

Ethylenediammonium Molybdates and Tungstate

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The preparations of tetraoxomolybdate, tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate stabilized by ethylenediammonium counter cation are described. The compounds are characterized by electronic and infrared spectral measurements, X-ray powder patterns and thermal studies. The thermogravimetric analyses suggest that in nitrogen atmosphere, the thiosalts decompose to give the respective metal disulphides.

AMMONIUM and alkali metal chalcogenomolybdates and chalcogenotungstates have been studied extensively by Müller and coworkers^{1,2}. As a part of our investigation on molybdates and tungstates stabilized by bulky amine-onium counter cations recently we have reported the characterization of morpholinium³, diethylammonium⁴ and N-ethylmorpholinium⁵ molybdates and tungstates. In this paper is reported the studies made on ethylenediammonium, $[\text{enH}_2]^{2+}$, tetraoxomolybdate, tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate. The compounds are examined by electronic and infrared spectral measurements, X-ray powder patterns and thermogravimetric analyses.

Experimental

All the chemicals used are commercially available pure reagent grade.

Preparation

Ethylenediammonium tetraoxomolybdate, $[\text{enH}_2]\text{-MoO}_4$, was prepared by dissolving about 4 g of MoO_3 in about 15 ml 50% aqueous en. The clear solution obtained was allowed to stand for crystallization. The separated prismatic crystals are collected on a filter washed with acetone and air-dried. Found: N, 12.2, Mo, 43.6%. Calc. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{Mo}$, N, 12.6, Mo, 43.2%.

Ethylenediammonium tetrathiomolybdate, $[\text{enH}_2]\text{-MoS}_4$, was prepared by passing hydrogen sulphide continuously for about 4 hr to an aqueous solution of ethylenediammonium molybdate containing small amount of free base. Red crystals of tetrathiomolybdate separated are filtered, washed with acetone and air-dried. Found: N, 9.52, S, 44.2, Mo, 32.8%. Calc. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_4\text{Mo}$, N, 9.79, S, 44.8, Mo, 33.5%.

Ethylenediammonium tetrathiotungstate, $[\text{enH}_2]\text{-WS}_4$, was obtained by passing hydrogen sulphide for about 4 hr to a clear solution of WO_3 in en. Yellow crystals separated in the initial stages are dissolved by warming the solution and continued the passing of hydrogen sulphide. The separated golden-yellow crystals are filtered, washed with acetone and air-

dried. Found: N, 7.21, S, 33.7, W, 48.6%. Calc. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_4\text{W}$, N, 7.49, S, 34.3, W, 49.1%.

Attempted isolation of ethylenediammonium tungstate either from WO_3 or from ammonium paratungstate was not successful.

Physical measurements

The electronic spectra of the compounds in water are measured employing Beckman DK2 and DBG7 spectrophotometers. The infrared spectra are taken on Perkin Elmer 225 spectrophotometer using CsI pellet technique. X-ray powder patterns are taken using Debye-Scherrer camera of 57.3 mm diameter employing X-rays of wavelength 1.5417 Å. The thermogravimetric analyses are made in air and nitrogen atmosphere using Stanton and Netzsch thermobalances.

Results and Discussion

The compounds are readily soluble in water and on acidification of the solutions, the tetraoxomolybdate precipitates out MoO_3 , whereas the tetrathiosalts give the respective metal trisulphides. The *d*-spacings of the compounds are given in Table 1 and the values suggest that the tetrathiosalts are isostructural. This is in agreement with the isomorphism^{6,7} of ammonium and alkali metal tetrathiomolybdates and tetrathiotungstates.

TABLE 1. X-RAY POWDER PATTERNS OF ETHYLENEDIAMMONIUM METALLATES (Å)

$[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoO}_4$	$[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoS}_4$	$[\text{enH}_2]\text{WS}_4$
5.31s	4.78s	4.77s
4.80s	3.26s	3.28s
4.19s	3.02m	3.01s
3.63s	2.71m	2.72s
3.34s	2.44s	2.46s
3.06s	2.36s	2.35s
2.30w	2.30m	2.29s
1.76w	2.00s	2.02s
1.71w	1.91s	1.92s
1.54w	1.64m	1.66s

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

Tetrathiomolybdate and Tetrathiotungstate are known⁶ to exhibit three characteristic electronic transitions in the visible and ultra-violet region. The electronic spectra of the thiosalts taken in water show three maxima with the molar absorptivity of the order 10^4 . The spectra are reproduced in Fig. 1 and the absorption maxima are given in Table 2. The spectral frequencies are assigned to the three lowest energy transitions, $t_1 \rightarrow 2e(\nu_1)$, $t_1 \rightarrow 4t_2(\nu_2)$ and $3t_2 \rightarrow 2e(\nu_3)$ according to Viste-Gray M.O. scheme⁸.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of $\text{enH}_2 \text{MoS}_4$ (---) and $\text{enH}_2 \text{WS}_4$ (—).

The tetraoxomolybdate is also expected to exhibit^{9,10} the corresponding three electronic transitions but only two absorptions in the region 200–230 nm are noticed. The other transition occurs below the limiting range of the generally available spectrophotometers. The spectral maxima observed at 225 and 211 nm for the tetraoxomolybdate are assigned⁸ to $t_1 \rightarrow 2e(\nu_1)$ and $3t_2 \rightarrow 2e(\nu_2)$.

Of the four fundamental vibrations of tetrahedral MX_4^{2-} ($M = \text{Mo}$ or W , $X = \text{O}$ or S) ions, ν_3 and ν_4 are infrared active¹¹. The tetraoxomolybdate

TABLE 2. ELECTRONIC AND INFRARED SPECTRAL FREQUENCIES OF ETHYLENEDIAMMONIUM METALLATES

Compound	Electronic (nm)			Infrared (cm^{-1})		
	225	221	—	890 m	830 s&b	330 m
$[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoO}_4$	465	316	241	480 sh,	470 s	
$[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoS}_4$	391	274	215	472 sh,	455 s	

s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder.

exhibits¹² i.r. bands due to ν_3 and ν_4 around 830 and 330 cm^{-1} , whereas the tetrathiomolybdate and tetrathiotungstate show^{10,13,14} the corresponding bands around 460 and 170 cm^{-1} . In our compound (Table 2) the i.r. bands observed at 835 (ν_3) and 330 cm^{-1} (ν_4) are characteristic of Mo-O stretching frequencies due to MoO_4 tetrahedral chromophore. A medium intensity band observed at 890 cm^{-1} is the forbidden band and its appearance may be due to the crystal field perturbation¹². The thiosalts showed bands around 470 cm^{-1} characteristic of M-S stretching frequency.

The thermogravimetric analysis of $[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoO}_4$ suggests that it starts decomposing around 220° and the decomposition is complete at 460°. The weight loss observed after completion of the decomposition was 35% and that calculated for the formation of MoO_3 is 35.2%. Chemical analysis of the decomposition product confirmed it to be MoO_3 .

The nature of thermal decomposition of the tetra-thiosalts is similar to that of ammonium¹⁵ and morpholinium³ tetrathiomethylates. The TG data are given in Table 3. The salts decompose in two stages; the first involving the formation of trisulphides and the second its subsequent decomposition. Both in air and nitrogen atmosphere the thiosalts start decomposing around 160° giving H_2S as one of the gaseous products. The first stage of decomposition is complete by 350°. The weight loss observed at this stage corresponds to the formation of metal trisulphides. On further rise in temperature, the trisulphides start decomposing giving metal trioxides in air and metal disulphides in nitrogen atmosphere around 460°. The chemical analyses of the residues confirmed the formation of $\text{M}^{\text{VI}}\text{O}_3$ and $\text{M}^{\text{IV}}\text{S}_2$ in air and nitrogen respectively.

TABLE 3. THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA ON ETHYLENEDIAMMONIUM TETRATHIOMETALLATES

Compound	Weight loss (%)						
	I stage			II stage			
	(Formation of MS_3)			(Formation of MO_3)		(Formation of MS_2)	
	Found	Calcd.		Air		N_2	
	Air	N_2	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
$[\text{enH}_2]\text{MoS}_4$	32.0	31.8	32.9	49.0	49.7	44.0	44.1
$[\text{enH}_2]\text{WS}_4$	22.0	21.0	22.5	38.0	38.1	34.0	33.7

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